

INVESTIGATION OF THE INTERPLY SLIP PROCESS IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Adrian M. Murtagh
Martin R. Monaghan
Patrick J. Mallon

University of Limerick
Ireland

ABSTRACT

When continuous fibre thermoplastic composites are sheet-formed into single or double curvature shapes, interply slip must occur in the resin rich layer between plies in order to avoid buckling and breakage of the fibres in the final part. An investigation has been carried out to examine this mechanism as it occurs in diaphragm forming. An experimental rig has been designed and built working on the principle of transversely drawing a central plate from between two flat specimen sections. Normal load, temperature, shear force and shear velocity can all be measured and controlled. A series of experiments have been carried out which investigate the effect of such variables as processing temperature, consolidation pressure, normal pressure during pullout and specimen layup, on shear stress. Various unidirectional and woven fibre material forms have been examined. A dead-weight loading system has been incorporated into the shearing rig which allows the yield shear stress to be measured. A model of the interply slip process is also presented.

Keywords : Thermoplastic composites, thermoforming, interply slip, yield stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced thermoplastic composites are a recent development in the materials industry and offer many advantages such as weight reduction, a high strength-to-weight ratio and good fatigue resistance over more conventional materials such as aluminium and steel. Compared to the more traditional thermoset composite materials, thermoplastic composites offer the designer faster cycle times, ease of storage and better impact properties. Laying-up of thermoplastic composites is relatively simple and the flat pre-preg sheet layup need only be heated and pressed into the desired shape, a process that may occur in seconds. Techniques already familiar to the metalforming industry have been adapted to the thermoforming process. Pressforming, in which the part is pressed between two matched metal-die moulds, and rubber pad forming, where one half of the mould is made from a compliant rubber material, are two such techniques [1]. Diaphragm forming is a new technique developed specifically for the sheet-forming of flat thermoplastic composite layups [2].

Despite all these advantages, manufacture of successful parts is hampered by a lack of knowledge regarding the actual forming mechanisms involved. The more complicated the geometry, the more complex the mechanisms and the more difficult it becomes for the designer to predict fibre orientation and distribution, and final part quality. For industries such as the aerospace industry, good quality and reproducibility is paramount. Problems such as void formation, fibre washing and fibre buckling must be avoided. To this end, research is ongoing in the search for a basic understanding of the flow mechanisms in thermoforming. This involves the measurement of rheological properties and the development of theoretical models and computer simulations which allow the prediction of final part geometry and avoid a 'hit-and-miss' situation. Thus a database can be created of processing conditions (temperature, pressure, forming rate, etc.) which will mean a good, high quality part been formed every time.

Four basic flow mechanisms have been identified [3] :

- 1) Resin percolation behaviour between the fibres
- 2) Transverse flow of the fibres
- 3) Interply slip (and rotation) of the individual plies across one another
- 4) Intraply shearing of the fibres within each ply (axially and transversely)

The more complex the part geometry, the more evident are the various mechanisms i.e. resin percolation need only take place when making a flat panel with a compliant top diaphragm, while all four mechanisms must occur when forming shapes such as complex curvature aerospace parts. This paper will endeavour to describe work carried out on investigating the interply slip phenomenon and determining the effect of processing temperature, pressure, part layup and material form on this mechanism. It is assumed that the plies behave as plates with slippage occurring in the thin resin interlayers.

Most of the work carried out to date has been done using APC-2, a unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PEEK matrix composite made by ICI. Glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP) has also been investigated. Tests with 'CETEX', made by Ten Cate, a carbon fibre/PEI fabric material has indicated that the reinforcement i.e. the fibre weave, has a major bearing on the behaviour of the interply slip mechanism.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Experimental Apparatus

The apparatus used to carry out the experimental investigation into interply slip consists of two parts ; (a) two heated platens contained in a DARTEC 100 kN hydraulic straining frame for consolidation and normal pressure application and (b) a custom-built shearing apparatus which provides the pulling out force to the central ply. The platens are embedded in insulation and heated by cartridge heaters and cooled using an air/water mixture passing through aluminium cooling plates. Process temperatures up to 400°C are possible with a maximum sample size of 150 mm x 150 mm. A motor driven leadscrew mechanism provides the basis for the shearing apparatus. A 500 N load cell measures shear force and a ± 150 mm LVDT measures ply displacement. All signals (temperature, load, etc.) are fed back through an A/D board to a PC on which the BASIC control program is run. All process variables are recorded and stored for future analysis. A simple dead-weight loading system utilising a pulley was used in the yield stress experiments. Figure 1, a schematic of the rig, shows the platens and position of the layup, including pullout ply and exterior plies. The entire apparatus, as shown in Figure 2, is more fully described in [4].

2.2. Experimental Procedure

Testing of samples involves soldering the plies together into the layup being tested, aligning and clamping between the platens and then applying a nominal contact pressure during heatup. Once processing temperature has been reached, the sample is allowed to rest for approximately 5 minutes to allow an even temperature distribution to develop. Commissioning results have shown the temperature to vary by $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ at 385°C for a 100 mm x 100 mm sample. A consolidation pressure of 1 MPa is applied for a period of time (5 minutes for a typical 7 ply APC-2 layup). Then testing may take place on the sample, either in the variable velocity or dead-weight shearing mode.

The convention used in describing layups is similar to the normal convention, with the $\bar{0}$ indicating symmetry about the central ply e.g. (0,90, $\bar{0}$)s, is a 0° exterior (clamped) ply, one 90° ply, then the same repeated symmetrically about a single 0° ($\bar{0}$) pullout ply.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effect of Varying Process Parameters

Various experiments have been carried out to investigate the interply slip behaviour, using APC-2 as the predominant material due to its good degree of fibre collimation and quality of prepreg. The effect of varying process temperature, consolidation pressure and normal pressure have been examined and results are presented in [4]. It was shown that an increase in temperature or a decrease in consolidation pressure had the effect of reducing shear stress levels. It must be remembered that increasing temperature too much may lead to problems such as resin migration and fibre wrinkling, and that a minimum consolidation pressure must be maintained in order to ensure good part integrity and to avoid void formation [5]. During interlaminar shear at a constant velocity and very low normal pressure, the shear stress reaches a peak value and then reduces quickly to a low level (Figure 3). As soon as normal pressure was increased, even by a small amount (0.25 kN = 25 kPa for 100 mm x 100 mm sample), the shear stress increased and then remained at constant level for this constant velocity. Further increases in normal pressure did not cause an increase in shear stress of the same magnitude. This condition more clearly represents diaphragm forming, where the layup is under vacuum pressure (100 kPa) throughout processing.

Figure 4 shows a plot of shear rate versus shear stress for various layups of APC-2. All variables (temperature = 385°C, consolidation pressure = 1 MPa, normal pressure during shearing = 100 kPa) are kept constant while the layup was varied. It is observed that much higher shear stresses occur in (0,0,0)s layups compared to other specimens. This may be due to the fact that fibres from one 0° ply penetrate into the fibres in the adjacent layer and thus causing interference, complicating the pullout behaviour. This phenomenon was found to be especially dependent on the normal pressure applied [6]. Physically, the fibres from the various plies became more entangled and misorientated as pullout continued. This fibre contact can also be seen when comparing the behaviour of a (0,90,0)s and a (0,90,90,0)s layup. One might expect the (0,90,90,0)s layup to be sheared more easily, due to the existence of an extra resin layer between the two 90° plies. During consolidation, the fibres from these plies appear to interact to form one body, a fact which is observed after pullout, when it can be seen that the two plies have deformed as a 'bulk'. Interlaminar rotation was seen to occur in the (0,30,0)s, (0,45,0)s and (0,60,0)s layups where the fibres in the angled plies tended to rotate in order to try and align themselves with the 0°-orientated fibres in the pullout ply i.e. in the direction of pullout.

3.2. Effect of Resin Layer Thickness

The interply slip behaviour of APC-2 is assumed to be dominated by the resin layer existing between the fibre-rich plies. Thus it should be the case that artificially increasing the thickness of this resin layer in some fashion should cause shearing to occur more easily, perhaps resulting in some method of circumventing problems such as buckling at bends, etc. One possibility that was examined involved placing thin 50 µm sheets of PEEK film between the plies of a sample layup and performing experiments to determine their effect on interply slip. The introduction of these sheets lubricated the slipping mechanism and lower shear stress levels were recorded than with ordinary APC-2 samples for the same shearing velocity. Increasing the number of sheets reduced shear stress still further. When shear rate values were calculated i.e. shear velocity/sheared thickness, it was shown that these PEEK layers resulted in a higher viscosity level than a sample without PEEK sheets (viscosity being the slope of shear rate versus shear stress). From Figure 5, it can be seen that at low shear rates, shear stresses for the samples using PEEK sheets are higher than for an ordinary (0,90,0)s sample. Thus it was observed that the PEEK sheets have a higher viscosity than the PEEK in the composite sample. The viscosity value for the PEEK film was calculated as approximately 2500 Pa.s. This value corresponds with typical values for high viscosity grade PEEK at these shear stresses [7]. APC-2 composite is based on a low grade viscosity resin, with a typical melt viscosity of 300 Pa.s. It has been observed that actual viscosity levels for the composite

may be up to 1.5 orders of magnitude above that for the neat PEEK resin [8]. In our case, viscosity levels for APC-2 were found to be 0.5 - 1 orders of magnitude above that of the PEEK resin for the normal pressures involved (100 kPa), thus implying fibre-fibre interaction to have an effect. In trying to increase the resin layer thickness, it must also be remembered that too much resin between the plies can cause other problems such as resin migration at bends. In some cases, the PEEK film had percolated through to the surface of the exterior ply causing waviness in the surface fibres.

3.3. Determination of Yield Stress

Thermoplastic composites exhibit a yield stress in the interply shear mode of deformation. Below this yield stress no ply slippage will occur. Above this critical value shearing will initiate and shear stress will increase with shear rate. In order to further examine this phenomenon, interply shear tests were carried out using a dead-weight loading system to apply the shear loads. A smaller ± 25 mm LVDT was utilised in order to determine when movement first occurs more accurately.

Figure 6 shows a plot of shear stress (dead weights) and displacement versus time. As can be seen, no displacement occurred for a $(90,0)_s$ layup under 25 kPa normal pressure until point A was reached where the shear stress is approximately 1.2 kPa. For a $(0,90,0)_s$ layup under similar conditions, the yield stress was approx 1 kPa.

Figure 7 is a similar plot, but for a $(0,0)_s$ layup which has undergone a slight compression (approximately 400 kPa) before dead weights were added under nominal contact pressure. It can be seen that as the shear stress increased to a level of about 2 kPa (region A) a slight movement of the ply was recorded (0.15 mm). When the shear stress was reduced to almost zero, the displacement recovered back to its original value. Thus an elastic mechanism is involved, possibly due to the contact between fibres from adjacent 0° plies. When the shear stress was increased again, irrecoverable slippage occurred at point B, about 3.2 kPa. As shear stress was reduced, the rate of shear decreased and movement finally stopped at a shear stress of approximately 2 kPa. It appears that a higher yield stress is involved, at least for the case in which the fibres in adjacent plies are parallel. The difficulty in obtaining results for this particular type of layup made validation of this characteristic difficult, but further investigation is ongoing.

The influence of normal pressure on yield stress is being investigated at present. This should show that for cross-ply laminates, the normal pressure should not have as great an effect as for laminates where adjacent plies are parallel and lie in the 0° direction. The effect of processing temperature on yield stress for a $(0,90,0)_s$ APC-2 sample was found to be insignificant.

3.4. C-Scans and Micrographs

C-scans were taken of samples both before and after interply slip had taken place. This was done for two reasons (i) to ensure that each sample was properly consolidated with no defects or voids before testing and (ii) to see if any fibre flow occurred at the rear of the sample between the two exterior plies which would not be observable to the naked eye. Most samples were shown to be of satisfactory quality with good consolidation characteristics. Figure 8 shows a scan of a $(0,90,0)_s$ APC-2 sample taken after testing. The flow pattern of the 90° ply in the centre can be seen at the centre-left of the scan which indicates the occurrence of transverse flow of this ply with barrelling [9]. The grey streaks to the left of this line are probably fibres left behind from the 90° ply during interply slip, showing that this ply did not behave as a rigid plate during slipping.

Sections were cut from various samples for microscopic analysis. After mounting them in Bakelite, the specimens were plane ground and polished using a $1 \mu\text{m}$ diamond disc. Difficulties arose due to the nature of the composite i.e. hard fibres in soft matrix, and scratches were evident across the surface of some samples. Figure 9 shows the details of a micrograph of a $(0,90,0)_s$ sample, showing the interface between the 0° and 90° plies. Fibres in the centre 0° ply (running parallel to the

page) are seen as long, almost elliptical, white dashes. A resin layer is evident, but it is certainly not constant thickness. In some places there are large amounts of matrix between the plies whereas in other places, fibres from each ply actually touch. The average height of the resin layer is approximately 1 fibre thickness or 6-7 μm . For a (0, $\bar{0}$)s and other layups where fibres from adjacent plies lay parallel, the interface was not so clear. The resin layer was barely evident, seen only as a very thin white line, dividing the two plies. Thus as observed previously, for this particular type of layup, fibre friction and intermingling appear to play a large part in hindering shear deformation between the layers. More work needs to be done to see how other variables such as normal pressure may affect the resin layer thickness.

3.5. Experimental Modelling

Typical Newtonian fluids show a linear relationship between shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) shear stress (τ), with a constant coefficient of viscosity. In more complex non-Newtonian fluids, this relationship becomes non-linear and viscosity does not remain constant with time. It is more common to refer to this viscosity as the 'apparent viscosity', defined as shear stress/shear rate [10]. For some plastics, known as pseudoplastics, the apparent viscosity decreases with shear rate. Other materials, known as Bingham bodies, exhibit a yield stress τ_{yield} above which there is a linear relationship between shear rate and shear stress. Thermoplastic long-fibre reinforced composites show a behaviour taking in aspects of Bingham bodies i.e. a yield stress, and a decreasing apparent viscosity with shear rate. These materials can be shown to obey the power law model :

$$\tau = \tau_{\text{yield}} + k \cdot \dot{\gamma}^n \quad (1)$$

where k and n are constants.

For thermoplastic composites, it is assumed shearing occurs in the resin rich layer between plies. If the resin layer thickness is known (typically 5% of one ply thickness), then the shear rate can be determined by

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{v}{nh_i} \quad (2)$$

where v is the shear velocity, n is the number of sheared layers and h_i is the resin layer thickness. The shear stress is the shear force divided by the sample area. From Equation (1), we can write

$$\log(\tau - \tau_{\text{yield}}) = \log k + n \log(\dot{\gamma}) \quad (3)$$

i.e. if we plot $\log(\text{shear stress} - \text{yield stress})$ vs $\log(\text{shear rate})$ and get a straight line, then a curve fit of the line will give the value of $\log k$ and n (constant and slope).

This was done for a (0,90, $\bar{0}$)s and a (0, $\bar{0}$)s layup and the results are shown in Figure 11. As well as including the yield stress in both cases, there is good correlation between the model and test results, with a slight divergence at higher shear rates. For the (0,90, $\bar{0}$)s layup with a yield stress of 1 kPa, $n = 0.6676$ and $k = 1.308$. For the (0, $\bar{0}$)s sample with a yield stress of 2 kPa, $n = 0.516$ and $k = 7.03$.

4. ALTERNATIVE MATERIAL FORMS

Besides APC-2, work has been carried out on GF/PP and CETEX (CF/PEI). Initial results for the GF/PP are similar to those for APC-2, except that the processing temperature and consolidation pressures are lower and slippage for the (0, $\bar{0}$)s layup seems to occur more easily, perhaps due to the lower volume fraction present. For CETEX however, matters are much more complex. The woven nature of this composite means that a constant resin layer thickness is impossible and fibre friction

probably plays a much larger part. Pullout is also complicated by the fact that fibres lying in the 90° direction tend to be left behind in the sample. Figure 12 shows a photograph of a sample where the pullout ply was at a $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation. The so-called 'trellis effect' is evident in the way that the pullout ply has 'necked' near the front of the sample. Results obtained from such tests are difficult to interpret as intraply shearing in the CETEX plies happens as a matter of course.

5. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental apparatus for performing interply slip experiments on continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites has been designed and built. The effect of temperature, consolidation pressure, normal pressure and layup has been examined. PEEK layers were used to try and increase the resin layer thickness but it was found that the grades of PEEK differ. Yield stress values have been determined for various layups of APC-2, indicating fibre contact to have a major effect in (0,0)s specimens, or in any specimen where fibres in adjacent plies lie parallel. A power law model incorporating yield stress has been developed for (0,90,0)s and (0,0)s layups. Work is ongoing in developing a more comprehensive set of model data for various layups and normal pressure conditions is ongoing. Work carried out on CETEX (woven CF/PEI) has shown the 'trellis effect' to be of major importance.

Further work needs to be carried out on such material forms as CETEX. Accurate determination of the resin layer thickness and an understanding of the degree of interaction between contacting fibres of different plies needs to be examined.

Acknowledgements

The funding for this project was provided through BREU-135 and the author would like to acknowledge the partners for permission to publish this work. The assistance and expertise provided by the Department of Mechanical and Production Engineering, University of Limerick is gratefully appreciated.

References

1. Okine, R.K., *Analysis of Forming Parts from Advanced Thermoplastic Composite Sheet Material*, SAMPE Journal, Vol. 25, No. 3, pp 50-76, 1989.
2. Mallon, P.J., O'Bradaigh, C.M., Pipes, R.B., *Polymeric Diaphragm Forming of Complex Curvature Thermoplastic Composite Parts*, Composites, Vol. 20, No. 1, 1989.
3. Cogswell, F.N., Leach D.C., *Processing Science of Continuous Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites*, SAMPE Journal, Vol. 24, No. 3, pp 11-14, 1988.
4. Murtagh A.M., Monaghan M.R., Mallon P.J., *Development of a Shear Deformation Apparatus to Characterize the Interply Slip Mechanism of Advanced Thermoplastic Composites*, Proc. IMF-8, UCD, Dublin, Ireland 1992.
5. Mulholland A.J., *Characterisation of Consolidation Flow Processes in Continuous Fibre-Reinforce Thermoplastic Composites*, M.Eng. Thesis, University of Limerick, 1992.
6. Scherer R., Friedrich K., *Inter- and Intraply-slip Flow Processes During Thermoforming of CF/PP-Laminates*, Composites Manufacturing, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 92-96, 1991.
7. Cogswell, F.N., *Thermoplastic Aromatic Polymer Composites*, Butterworth-Heinemann Ltd, Oxford, England, 1992.
8. Scobbo, J.J., Nakajima N., *Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Molten Thermoplastic / Continuous Graphite Fiber Composites in Simple Shear Deformation*, 21st Intl. SAMPE Tech. Conf., pp 730-739, 1989.
9. Barnes, J.A., Cogswell, F.N., *Transverse Flow Processes in Continuous Fibre-Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites*, Composites, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp 38-42, 1989.
10. Brydson J.A., *Flow Properties of Polymer Melts*, Iliffe Books, London, England 1970.

Figure 1 Schematic of test rig

Figure 2 Experimental apparatus

Figure 3 Effect of normal pressure

Figure 4 Layup variation

Figure 5 Effect of PEEK sheets

Figure 6 Yield stress of (90,0)s sample

Figure 7 Yield stress of $(0,0)_s$ layup

Figure 8 C-Scan of tested $(0,90,0)_s$ panel

Figure 9 Details of micrograph for $(0,90,0)_s$ sample

Figure 11 Experimental versus model data

Figure 12
'Trellis effect' on $\pm 45^\circ$ CETEX